

The Man Defining the Epoch: Mamat Haydarov

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Abstract

There are people from every period who contributed to the development of this stage, overcoming difficulties. They all represent some aspect of society. Mamat Khaydarov is one such hardworking scientist. An article about the scientist, statesman and common man Mamat Khaydarov, who made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek pedagogy. The article describes the difficult scientific path of the scientist, his work, scientific and managerial activities, as well as his role in the development of Uzbek science.

Keywords: Mamat Khaydarov, management, science, school, social activities,

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Introduction

History is constantly changing. From century to century, from year to year, its weight increases, and the content becomes richer. Although all events and individuals went down in history, we cannot say that they all contributed to the development of society, state and science. All eras have their own scientists, people who determined the epoch. These are people who experienced the hardships of that time, who strive to improve society, educate an ideal person and, therefore, attract the attention of society. One of such great people is Mamat Khaydarov, a famous scientist and statesman, a modest person who made a great contribution to Uzbek pedagogy. This article is about the science and lifestyle of a scientist.

Brief biography

Mamat Eshkulovich Khaydarov was born in 1960 in the Termez district of the Surkhandarya region. He is Uzbek by nationality with higher education, a member of the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, graduated from the Termez State Pedagogical Institute in 1982, and in 2005 from the Tashkent State Financial Institute.

He began his career in 1982-1985 as a teacher at the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology at the Termez State Pedagogical Institute. 1986-1988 He was a full-time graduate student of the Institute of Pedagogical Sciences named after T.N. Kori Niyazi, 1989-1992 - Associate Professor of the Department of Primary Education of the Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute named after Nizami, Dean of the Evening Department of the Faculty of Elementary Education. From 1996 to 1998 - Secretary of the Academic Council of the University, from 1999 to 2006 - Dean of the Faculty of Primary Education and Defectology, from 2006 to 2009 - Vice-Rector for Scientific Work of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, from 2009 to 2017 was the rector of Termez State University. From 2017 to the present - Professor of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, a member of the Council of Rectors of Europe and the Council of Rectors under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Education.

Mamat Eshkulovich Khaydarov Candidate of Science Degree, 1988 and in 2000 he received his Doctor of Science Degree. [8] In 1996 he was promoted to associate professor, in 2001 - professor.

From 2005 to 2010, he served as secretary of the Council for Pedagogical Sciences, specialty K113.18.03 of the Higher Attestation Commission under the Cabinet of Ministers, and since 2001 - secretary, chairman of the specialized council D067.18.03. It should be noted that for the first time, on the initiative and proposal of M.E. Khaydarov Scientific Councils opened at 13.00.06 - Theory and methods of teaching and special pedagogy 13.00.03.

Science

Under the guidance of the scientist, 8 doctors of philosophy (PhD) and doctors of science (DSc) were trained. Professor Khaydarov Mamat Eshkulovich is a scientist who made a worthy contribution to pedagogical science, more than 148 scientific articles have been published in prestigious scientific journals in Japan, the Czech Republic and Russia [6, 7, 3, 17, 18, 22, 23, 25, 27], more than 12 author of textbooks, teaching aids and teaching aids, 5 monographs [11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 21, 24].

He also contributed to the development of over 20 PhDs and over 80 PhDs during his tenure as Chairman of the Specialized Pedagogical Council.

His contribution to the development of science, effective work on the training of young scientists and specialists brought him the respect of the domestic and international scientific community.

Management

The famous scientist, organizer, knowledgeable intellectual Mamat Eshkulovich Khaydarov attracted the attention of scientists and our people with his modest, but at the same time, all-round merit in science. M. Khaydarov is a truly patriotic, patriotic teacher-scientist, his arrival as rector of Termez State University in 2009 radically changed the spiritual image of the university. Thanks to tireless work during the construction and commissioning of the main building of the university, organizational skills, efforts to rally the team, he attracted the attention of the leadership of our country.

During M. Khaydarov's tenure as rector, professors and teachers of Termez State University won 6 state grants and 4 foreign grants in the competition of state scientific and technical programs for fundamental research. 97 textbooks and 22 monographs have been published. Author of 132 scientific articles and dissertations at international scientific conferences. 26 professors and teachers were awarded the title of "University Professor", 23 - the title of "Associate Professor of the University", and 12 were awarded the badge of distinction in the field of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the field of education and science in 2012-2014, 6 students became owners of the state scholarship named after A. Navoi and 3 students became owners of the state scholarship named after M. Ulugbek, 6 students took pride of place at the republican stage of the Olympiad in science. Scientific, scientific and practical, scientific and theoretical, scientific and technical conferences and conferences were held at the university level 30, at the national level 7 and 1 international scientific and technical conference. In the spiritual and educational sphere in 2012-2014, more than 6,130 events were held, 16,027 students were enrolled. Over the past period, students of the university have won 23 gold, 20 silver and 38 bronze medals at republican and international competitions in the field of sports.

M. Khaydarov paid special attention to the development of education, which is the basis of the Uzbek national mentality, and showed that he is a leader-organizer.

Science School

M. Khaydarov is one of the famous scientists who made a worthy contribution to the further development of science in Uzbekistan, the training of educated and intellectually gifted personnel, and the support of talented youth. On his initiative, scientific cooperation was established with the University of Soka in Japan, the University of Vyatautas the Great in Lithuania, the University of Groningen in the Netherlands, the University of Balkh in Afghanistan, the Charles University in the Czech Republic, the University of Pisa in Italy, Giessen, Halle, Weinstein University in Germany, the University of Santiago- de Brittany and the University of Santiago de Compostello in Spain, also the German Embassy in Uzbekistan and the Goethe Institute.

He is the author of textbooks and teaching aids on methods of educational work, Uzbek folk pedagogy, an explanatory dictionary of pedagogy, comparative pedagogy, Uzbek national traditions, life lessons [21]. It is also worth noting that the second edition of "Ontology of Uzbek Pedagogy" in 2010 was published under the general editorship of M. Khaydarov [20]. He is one of the authors who have made a significant contribution to the development of the concepts "The concept of raising children", "Pedagogy", "Labor education in the system of continuous education."

For merits in the field of pedagogy, the pedagogical activity of the scientist is included in the collection of Uzbek pedagogy, published in 1999 by the Publishing House of the Teacher [19]. In 2005, he initiated a retraining course for applied defectologists, and in 2009, a refresher and retraining course for teachers of archeology and ethnography.

M. Khaydarov was the organizer of the International Conferences "Development of Science in the Continuing Education System" in 2007, "The Role and Significance of Struggle in the Education of the Younger Generation" in 2011, "Women Scientists of the Republic", "Educational Environment", "Problems of Harmonious Education", "Developed generation" and many other republican conferences.

Public Activity

M. Khaydarov In 2009 and 2015 he was a deputy of the Surkhandarya Regional Council of People's Deputies [9], in 2012 and 2015 he was elected a member of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan [4, 9, 10]. Awarded with the sign of the 20th anniversary of the Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Mamat Khaydarov In 2009-2014, Mamat Eshkulovich Khaydarov was elected a member of the Committee on Science, Education, Culture and Sports in accordance with the decision of the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On registration as a member of M. Khaydarov of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [2]. In 2015-2018, by the decision of the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the registration of M. Khaydarov as a member of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan" he was elected a deputy. Foreign Policy Committee [1]. Currently, he is a member of the Expert Commission on Pedagogical Sciences of the Higher Attestation Commission under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

M.E. Khaydarov is a calm, disciplined, responsible and at the same time kind and generous person. Everything requires discipline, norms, responsibility and diligence. He also prefers perseverance in work, diligence in science, and perseverance in faith. Thanks to his life principles, he has reached his current status, level of knowledge and prestige.

As a scientist, he always strives for innovation, tries to introduce innovations into life and science. Applies new pedagogical technologies and methods in the educational process, strives to improve the effectiveness of teaching.

When we look at the work of a scientist, we see that he is an active, energetic, inquisitive person in everything. We can say that the work of M. Khaydarov, the scientific school created by him, the scientific heritage will become the basis for including the scientist in the list of people who determined the era. In 2020, the scientist turned 60. We wish M. Khaydarov many years of life, good health, fruitful work in science, organizational and political success, happiness of his children in family life. Always be in the spotlight, surrounded by students!

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